

ATIP/A*CRC Workshop on

Accelerator Technologies for High-Performance Computing: *Does Asia Lead the Way?*

Programme Handbook

May 7 – 10, 2012
Matrix Building, Biopolis, Singapore

Sponsored by US National Science Foundation (NSF) and select leading HPC vendors

Location of the Workshop

Matrix Building, 30 Biopolis Street 138671

Welcome Message

It is a great pleasure to welcome all participants to this workshop. We are especially happy to have many visitors from other Asia Pacific countries and the United States.

In the November 2011 ranking of the world's most powerful supercomputers, four out of the top five most powerful systems were built in Japan or China. Three of these five systems boast GPU accelerators. It is an opportune time to analyze the current state-of-the-art accelerated HPC architectures from an Asian perspective and experience, including practical issues of use, code development, and performance, as well as the advantages and limitations of accelerated HPC systems.

With support from the United States National Science Foundation (NSF) and in cooperation with the HPC Special Interest Group (HPC SIG) of the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), the Asian Technology Information Program (ATIP) and the Agency for Science, Technology and Research (A*STAR) Computational Resource Centre (A*CRC), this workshop in Singapore focus on the practical aspects of scientific and engineering applications, experiences with program development, porting, tuning, performance optimization, efficiency, hardware utilization, time to solution, and the outlook for near-future trends and prospects for accelerated HPC.

We believe it will be a very fulfilling two days with the presentations covering a wide spectrum of the accelerated HPC practice. Some tutorial sessions arranged by vendors will be conducted on the third and fourth day.

Additionally, we have arranged for site visits to some of Singapore's premier research labs and HPC centre in the universities. We hope this will provide a good opportunity, especially for our foreign visitors, to learn about some of the research work conducted locally and explore potential collaborations.

We believe everyone will have a fruitful workshop and we thank you for participating.

Dr. David Kahaner
ATIP President

Dr. Marek Michalewicz
Senior Director, A*CRC

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ATIP/A*CRC Workshop Organization

Organizing Committee:

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Prof. Jack Dongarra, University of Tennessee
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Program Timetable

7 May 2012				
Location	Exploration Theatre			
Time	Speaker	Title		
08:00 - 08:30	Registration			
08:30 - 08:40	David KAHANER Marek MICHALEWICZ	Welcome Address		
08:40 - 08:50	Raj THAMPURAN, Executive Director, SERC, A*STAR	Welcome Speech		
08:50 - 09:30	Keynote 1 Satoshi MATSUOKA Tokyo Institute of Technology, JAPAN	Accelerating Beyond Petaflops --- Issues and Prospects		
09:30 - 10:05	Lecture 1 Michael LEVINE Pittsburgh Supercomputing Center, USA	Computational Accelerators in the US/NSF Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment		
10:05 - 10:20	Coffee/Tea Break			
10:20 - 10:55	Lecture 2 Wei GE State Key Laboratory of Multi-phase Complex Systems, Institute of Process Engineering (IPE), Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), CHINA	Petaflops Simulation in Chemical and Process Engineering		
Location	Exploration Theatre		Discovery Theatre	
	Chair: Marek MICHALEWICZ Applications 1: CFD		Chair: TBA Infrastructure 1	
10:55 -	G. SUDHAKARAN	<i>A GPU Computing Platform (Saga) and a</i>	Hiroaki KOBAYASHI	<i>Capability of Vector-Parallel Computing</i>

Site Visit Schedule

Time	Location
9 May 2012	
09:00	Meet at Matrix Building lobby
09:15 – 10:00	BII
10:10 – 11:00	ETC
11:10 – 12:00	GIS
12:00 – 13:30	Lunch at own expense in Matrix Building Food Court
13:30 – 13:45	Meet at Matrix Building lobby, travel to Fusionopolis
14:00 – 14:45	IHPC
14:50 – 15:30	A*CRC
15:30 – 16:10	I ² R
16:15 – 17:00	DSI
17:00 – 17:30	Travel to Matrix Building
10 May 2012	
09:00 – 09:15	Meet at Matrix Building lobby, travel to NUS
09.30 – 10:30	NUS
10:45 – 11:30	IMRE
11:45 – 13:00	Lunch at own expense in NUS Canteen
13:00 – 13:30	Travel to NTU
13:30 – 14:15	NTU
14:15 – 15:00	Travel to Matrix Building lobby

Abstracts

Keynote Lecture

Accelerating Beyond Petaflops --- Issues and Prospects

Prof. Matsuoka SATOSHI
Tokyo Institute of Technology

While heterogeneous architectures with hybrid throughput-oriented many-core and latency-sensitive multi-core are deemed to be the future towards exascale computing, many open technological issues remain.

Based on our experiences on TSUBAME2.0, one of the world's leading GPU many-core accelerated petaflops supercomputers, we investigate the forefronts such issues, identifying the challenges as well as their possible solutions.

Lecture

Computational Accelerators in the US/NSF Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment

Michael LEVINE
Pittsburgh Supercomputing Center (PSC), USA

The US/NSF Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment (XSEDE) program provides advanced research cyberinfrastructure to the open science community with advanced computing, visualization, storage, and networking resources and the associated expertise to use those resources.

In response to the expanding needs of the research community and the availability of new technologies, NSF resources are diversifying to include such technologies including computational accelerators in current and upcoming production systems. We will review those activities including some of the recent and anticipated research application advances.

Lecture

Petaflops simulation in chemical and process engineering

Wei GE
State key Laboratory of Multi-phase Complex Systems, Institute of Process Engineering (IPE), Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), CHINA

Chemical engineering, or in a boarder sense, process engineering, is bridging vast scale difference between molecular structures that define the properties or functions of the chemical products and the reactors or equipments that actually produce these materials, typically from 10-10m and 10-15s to 101m and 103s. Bottlenecks are faced at the so-called meso-scales [1] where neither detailed dynamical study nor lumped statistical study seems to be sufficient or matured. Examples can be found in nano- and micro-fluidics, turbulent eddies and particle clusters in multiphase reaction systems, etc.

The supercomputing capabilities available currently has provided an unique opportunity to improve

our understanding at these meso-scales. In this presentation, we will demonstrate that, through consistent designing of the physical and mathematical models and the computer software and hardware [2], rigorous molecular dynamics (MD) can now reach truly Petaflops sustainable performance and micron scales in three dimensions or even millimeter scales in at least one dimension, which are reasonably "macro-scales" for statistical studies. For example, using up to 1728 GPUs of the Mole-8.5 system at IPE (<http://www.top500.org/list/2010/06/100>), a complete influenza virion, H1N1, constructed by 300 million atoms or radicals including the aqueous solution, is simulated at a speed of 0.77 ns per day [3]. Virtual experiments, such as the docking of the drugs can be conducted. In another example, using all CPUs and GPUs of the Tianhe-1A system (<http://www.top500.org/system/10587>), the silane pyrolysis and silicon deposition processes for the production of high-purity crystalline silicon were simulated with more than 100 billion atoms. The sustainable performance for the simulation of the bulk of silicon crystal has reached 1.87 Petaflops in single precision using all 7168 GPUs of Tianhe-1A [4].

Based on the strategy demonstrated in these examples, general purpose software and hardware platforms for high performance computing (HPC) of MD simulation can be established, which will proven to be a very powerful tool for exploring meso-scale structures, especially the fascinating nano- and micro-scale structures in chemical engineering.

Applications Session 1: Computational Fluid Dynamics

A GPU Computing Platform (Saga) and a CFD Code On GPUs For Aerospace Applications

G. SUDHAKARAN

Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, INDIAN SPACE RESEARCH ORGANISATION (ISRO), INDIA

A GPU based supercomputer, SAGA (Supercomputer for Aerospace with GPU Architecture) is developed in VSSC using Intel processors and nVidia GPUs. The supercomputer presently consists of 436 numbers of Intel Quad Core Xeon processors and 436 nVidia Tesla C2070 GPUs (FERMI). Each FERMI GPU has a double precision (DP) floating point performance of 515 GFLOPS. Individual nodes of the supercomputer are configured with two CPUs and two GPUs to have 1:1 ratio. The nodes are disk-less machines using compressed RAM file system. 40 Gbps QDR Infiniband network is used for inter-process communication between the nodes and Gigabit Ethernet interface is used for network booting of the nodes and user interface. SAGA uses in-house configured Linux Operating System. The cluster resource manager and job scheduler are developed in-house to manage the operation of entire supercomputer. SAGA has a theoretical peak performance of 240 TFLOPS (DP). The supercomputer will be augmented to 400 TF by adding another 150 nodes comprising of 300 numbers of nVidia Tesla M2090 GPUs and 300 numbers of Intel 6-core Xeon processors by April 2012.

Cartesian grid based Computational Fluid Dynamics code PARAS-3D is the major application software running on SAGA. PARAS-3D code was written for GPUs using CUDA programming model provided by nVidia. PARAS-3D has about 2.5 lakh lines of C-code and is one of the complex applications running on GPUs. The code is extensively used by ISRO and other aerospace organizations in the country. The advantages of PARAS-3D includes fully automatic grid generation, ability to handle complex geometries, interface for CAD geometries, adaptive grid refinement etc.

GPUs inherit their architecture from traditional graphics processors and are SIMD (Single Instruction Multiple Data) processors. Accordingly, to extract good performance from GPUs, the algorithm must be designed in a data parallel fashion. PARAS-3D software with its adaptive cartesian grids and with oct-tree data structure, is not inherently data parallel. With suitable algorithms, it was made more data parallel by arranging cells into different groups having varying

levels of data-parallelism. In this process the most complex set of computations will be assigned to CPUs. GPUs have limited set of registers and cache. Memory management is very important for getting good performance from GPUs. The update operations between CPU and GPU was programmed as a single update. The number of local variables are optimized to keep them within the cache to the extend possible. A single code is used for both CPUs and GPUs, which is capable of identifying the CPUs and GPUs in a machine and configures automatically.

With the above modifications, PARAS gives very good performance in GPU systems. The software uses the three technologies for high performance computing, namely, distributed computing, shared memory computing and GPU accelerators. The speed-up obtained for CFD problems for a single GPU node consisting of 2 Quad Core Xeon processors and 2 GPUs is 4.5 to 7 times compared to a single CPU node having 2 Quad Core Xeon processors. The speed up depends on the complexity of the geometry, flow gradients and size of the problem under consideration. PARAS gives 90 % efficiency upto 40 nodes. In general, about 1 million cells per GPU gives very good performance (> 90 %) upto 40 nodes.

Object-oriented Pseudo-spectral code TARANG for turbulence simulation

Mahendra K. VERMA
Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur (IITK), INDIA

Pseudo-spectral algorithm is one of the most accurate method for solving fluid flows. We have developed a general-purpose flow solver named Tarang (synonym for waves in Sanskrit) for turbulence and instability studies. Tarang is a parallel and modular code written in object-oriented language C++. Using Tarang, we can solve incompressible flows involving pure fluid, Rayleigh-Bénard convection, passive and active scalars, magnetohydrodynamics, liquid-metals, etc.

We have demonstrated that Tarang and its associate spectral transforms (e.g., Fast Fourier Transform) scale almost linearly to 16000 CPU processors on Bluegene computer of KAUST. We are porting the code to GPGPU platform, and the initial results are very encouraging. We will present the scaling studies of Tarang on CPU and GPGPU platforms.

Thermostat for colloidal dynamics simulations: Some challenges

P.B. Sunil KUMAR
IIT Madras, INDIA

Simulating colloidal dynamics, with solvent mediated hydrodynamic interactions, is a challenging task. The traditional approach is to use Dissipative Particle Dynamics thermostat and soft interactions. However this can yield only low Schmidt numbers. We have implemented an MPI version of Lowe-Anderson thermostat, with soft interactions, to obtain fluids with high Schmidt numbers. Some results from the simulations of living polymers, with this thermostat, is presented.

Infrastructure Session

Capability of Vector-Parallel Computing Platforms

Hiroaki KOBAYASHI
Tohoku University, JAPAN

In my talk, after briefly describing a supercomputing system of Tohoku University, I will show you the performance of real science and engineering applications on modern computing platforms such as SX-9, Nehalem-EX/EP, Fujitsu FX and GPU clusters. In addition, I will present our recent research work on design of a chip multi-vector core processor architecture and its implementation by using the 3D die-stacking technology. The early evaluation of the implementation will also be presented in terms of the performance per power improvement compared with the conventional 2D implementation.

Accelerating your HPC Environment

William LU
Platform, USA

In this presentation, we will provide an overview of the latest technologies from Platform Computing that maximize utilization of the IT resources and accelerate performance of the cluster environment. Technologies such as Platform LSF provide a powerful workload manager for demanding, distributed and mission-critical high performance computing environments. We will also discuss methods for taking maximum advantage of GPU capabilities through workload scheduling configuration strategies.

The Challenge and Opportunity of Smart City to High Performance Computing

Shengzhong FENG
Institute of Advanced Computing and Digital Engineering, Shenzhen Institute of Advanced Technology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, CHINA

Smart city and smart planet are the new stages of global information development. As the core technology for the development of smart city, high performance computing got new challenges and opportunities. The challenges of smart city to high performance computing include: massive data computing, real-time computing, social computing and effective computing. Shenzhen Institutes of Advanced Technology (SIAT), Chinese Academy of Sciences, is working on these areas; the latest development and infrastructure built at SIAT are summarized in this paper.

Keynote Lecture

HA-PACS Project: Challenge for Next Step of Accelerated Computing

Taisake BOKU
University of Tsukuba, JAPAN

HA-PACS Project is a 3-year project in CCS, University of Tsukuba, to develop a new generation of large scale GPU cluster for research on wide area of computational science as well as the research and development of new technology for interconnection network for parallel processing with accelerators. In this talk, the project overview and status report is provided.

The coverage application area of HA-PACS project includes particle physics, astrophysics, biophysics, geoscience, etc. The base cluster system with 800 TFLOPS of peak performance is dedicated. Moreover, we are developing a new technology to reduce the communication latency among parallel GPUs over different nodes supported by the concept of Tightly Coupled Accelerators (TCA). To develop a prototype of TCA, we use FPGA system to enable direct communication between GPUs on PCI-Express address space without help of CPU. Through this

research, we will develop an elemental technology to realize the fast communication among accelerators for wide area of applications.

The base cluster system of HA-PACS has started its operation from February 2012, with ultra high speed node employing two Intel E5 (SandyBridge) CPUs and four NVIDIA Tesla M2090 to provide 2.99 TFLOPS of peak performance, which is currently the world fastest GPU accelerated node for massively cluster system. The number of nodes is 268 to provide a performance of 802 TFLOPS as peak. Various computational science teams are working to develop large scale GPU accelerated codes, and HA-PACS base cluster will be dedicated for the development of them. The first prototype of TCA is under development and HA-PACS base cluster will be extended in early 2013 with 200+ TFLOPS of performance equipped with TCA.

Applications Session 2A: Molecular Dynamics

SC_PEtot: A Plane Wave Pseudopotential Density Functional Theory Code on GPU Clusters

Long WANG
Computer Network and Information Center, CAS, CHINA

In this talk, I will introduce the growing use of GPU in China, and our plan to develop GPU based applications. I will also introduce a most recently GPU work: SC_PEtot, which is developed by SCCAS, LBNL, and Fudan University, to speedup the Plane wave pseudopotential (PWP) density functional theory (DFT) calculation.

PWP-DFT is the most widely used material science simulation, and the PWP-DFT codes are arguably the most important material science codes. We have implemented a PWP DFT code PEtot on a multi-node GPU machine. As we know, it's the first code using multi-GPU to do PWP DFT calculations. In this talk, we will introduce the wavefunction transfer algorithm which can break the bottleneck on GPU FFT calculations. We will also introduce other optimization skills used in SC_PEtot code.

Accelerating Molecular Dynamics on Heterogeneous Petascale Supercomputer

Chun HUANG
School of Computer, National University of Defense Technology (NUDT), CHINA

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation is frequently used in the study of nanoscale physical phenomena. How to accelerate it on TianHe-1A, a GPU-accelerated heterogeneous petascale system? We consider both the performance and scalability issues of MD simulations on TianHe-1A. A hybrid MPI-OpenMP-CUDA programming model is adopted to exploit parallelism within one node and across the nodes. An effective multi-level dynamic load balancing strategy is used to adjust the workload. Computation and communication overlapping technology between CPU cores and GPUs within one node effectively hides communication latency. Besides, some other effective accelerate technologies are discussed.

Scaling Fast Multipole Methods up to 4000 GPUs

Rio YOKOTA
King Abdullah University of S&T, SAUDI ARABIA

The Fast Multipole Method (FMM) is a hierarchical N-body algorithm with linear complexity, high

arithmetic intensity, high data locality, has hierarchical communication patterns, and no global synchronization. The combination of these features allows the FMM to scale well on large GPU based systems, and to use their compute capability effectively. However, the FMM is a fairly complicated algorithm and its implementation using a hybrid MPI/OpenMP/CUDA environment involves many nontrivial decisions in the design of the code. I will introduce some of the recent efforts in FMMs for large scale accelerator based systems.

Applications Session 2B: Genomics, etc

Accelerate High Throughput Analysis for Genome Sequencing with GPU

Bingqiang WANG
Beijing Genomics Institute (BGI), CHINA

After digitizing DNA double helix by sequencing, computation is the key connecting raw sequences with life science discoveries. As massive data is generated, how to process and analyze as well as store them in an efficient manner turns out to be a major challenge. By developing GPU accelerated bioinformatics tools and integrate them into pipelines, BGI researchers now run analysis pipelines in several hours instead of several days. The speed up is generally around 10-50x comparing with traditional counterparts. Also accessing data efficiently is another obstacle to maximize throughput, this could be leveraged by compression technology.

CUDA technology applications in studies of disease-causing viruses

Victor A KOSTYUCHENKO
Duke-NUS Singapore, SINGAPORE

A process of restoration (reconstruction) of a three-dimensional structure from its two-dimensional projections is very computation-intensive, thus a great target for GPGPU-assisted acceleration. Application of CUDA technology with nVidia Fermi hardware allowed a speed-up of 100 to 1000 times for different stages of image processing and 3d reconstruction, compared to the standard CPU implementation. The object of three-dimensional reconstruction presented is Barmah Forest virus, a mosquito-borne virus that is currently a rising public health concern in Australia. The obtained three-dimensional structure at sub-nanometer resolution allowed a detailed look into the virus' organization as well as virus particle assembly process and revealed possible antiviral drug targets.

Hardware Accelerators in Scientific Applications: A Monte Carlo Case Study

Hongsuk YI
KISTI Supercomputing Center, KOREA

We present a heterogeneous implementation of several application accelerators executing the simple Diffusion Monte Carlo, a simulation method widely used in physics and physical chemistry for the electronic structure of realistic materials. Quantum Monte Carlo is naturally scalable to a large number of many-cores architectures such as in the case of heterogeneous GPU accelerated systems. We exploit the enormous amount of data parallelism on GPUs to accelerate the computationally intensive functions of the algorithm using OpenCL paradigm. We show that OpenCL provides application portability between multicore processors and GPUs and explicit vectorization implementations is found to be critical to achieving good performance of this algorithm on both CPU and GPUs. We discuss initial results from code implementation, and plans

for variants of other GPU-accelerated molecular dynamics simulation of solid covalent crystals. Together, we discuss initial results from our code implementation for variants of other hardware accelerators as a starting point for investigating related scientific applications on future heterogeneous architectures.

Keynote Lecture

Virtual Try On: An Application That Needs GPU Acceleration

Nadia THALMANN
Nanyang Technological University, SINGAPORE

Since more than 10 years, we have been working on simulating 3D clothes. Until recently, due to the calculation time, it was almost impossible to calculate this simulation in real-time. Now, we are working on an application that allows the user to choose her size, model her body as hers and try a few garments on her body. She can also modify the size of the garment and sees how it fits.

This type of application needs computer acceleration as it is very difficult to run it in real-time. The application does not only contain static image of the person but sequences of animation. This means that 25 images per second have to be generated in real-time including body deformations, physical based simulation and collision detection of the cloth with the body and the cloth with itself.

In this presentation, we will explain what are the problems to be solved with case studies.

Graphics, Visualisation, Imaging

The Multi-Modal Australian ScienceS Imaging and Visualisation Environment (MASSIVE)

Wojtek GOSCINSKI
Monash University, AUSTRALIA

The Multi-modal Australian ScienceS Imaging and Visualisation Environment (MASSIVE) is a specialised Australian high performance computing facility for computational imaging and visualisation. This facility, which runs a heterogeneous GPU cluster, has been formed to provide researchers with the hardware, software and expertise to drive research in the characterization, biomedical science, materials research, engineering, and geoscience communities, and stimulate advanced imaging research that will be exploited across a range of imaging modalities, including synchrotron imaging, neuroimaging, electron microscopy and optical microscopy. This presentation will introduce the MASSIVE project, and it's use of GPUs to provide a near-realtime Computed Tomography (CT) reconstruction service for the Imaging and Medical Beamline (IMBL) at the Australian Synchrotron. An analysis that illustrates the need to include GPUs in the system solution will be presented.

Single-particle 3D Reconstruction on Specialized Stream Architecture and Comparison with GPGPUs

Guangming TAN
Institute of Computing Technology (ICT), CAS, CHINA

The wide acceptance and the data deluge in medical imaging processing require faster and more efficient systems to be built.

Due to the advances in heterogeneous architectures recently, there has been a resurgence in research aimed at FPGA-based as well as GPGPU-based accelerator.

In this paper, on one side, we quantitatively analyze the workload, computational intensity and memory performance of a single-particle 3D reconstruction application, called *EMAN*, and parallelized it on a CUDA GPGPU architecture. We decouple the memory operations from the computing flow and orchestrate the thread-data mapping to reduce the overhead of off-chip memory operations.

On the other side, we exploit the trend towards FPGA-based accelerator design, which is achieved by offloading computing-intensive kernels to dedicated hardware modules.

Furthermore, a customized memory subsystem is also designed to facilitate the decoupling and optimization of computing dominated data access patterns.

We evaluate the proposed accelerated strategies by comparing to a parallel program on a 4-cores CPU. The CUDA version on a GTX480 shows a speedup of about 6 times. The stream architecture is implemented on a Xilinx Virtex LX330 FPGA and is justified by the reported 2.54 times speedup. Meanwhile, measured in terms of power efficiency, our FPGA-based accelerator outperforms a 4-cores CPU and a GTX480 by 7.33 times and 3.4 times, respectively.

Infrastructure & Activities

CSIR initiatives in Petascale Computing

R.P. THANGAVELU
CMMACS, INDIA

Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) is a premier R&D organization in India whose geographical spread extends over the whole country while its scientific spread touches virtually all fields of science and technology including aerospace, biology, chemistry, earth sciences, engineering and physical sciences etc. CSIR has 37 laboratories and several units. CSIR Centre for Mathematical Modelling and Computer Simulation (C-MMACS) is located in Bangalore and was started in the year 1988. One of the mandates of C-MMACS is to provide HPC access to the scientific workforce of CSIR which is nearly 4500 strong. The early HPC initiatives began in the CSIR National Aerospace Laboratories (NAL) with the installation of Univac in the year 1984 prior to the establishment of C-MMACS. By 1994 the Univac system was retired and C-MMACS established the first supercomputer of CSIR: Convex C3820 with two vector processors and 240 Mflops speed. From then on, the HPC capability has largely been concentrated in C-MMACS and has grown over the years at a steady rate. In the year 2005, CSIR IGIB established a compute cluster which was then the fastest in India. Apart from this, all major HPC infrastructure is being planned, installed and operated by C-MMACS for CSIR. By October 2012, C-MMACS will have India's fastest supercomputer rated at 300 Teraflops sustained on HPL. This is a major leap from earlier installation of 133 Teraflops system by CRL, India. With CSIR's vision to embrace simulation and data centric science, C-MMACS is presently engaged in planning for state-of-the-art high performance computing system during the 12th Five Year Plan (2012-17).

The application environment in C-MMACS HPC facility is rich with in-house developed, open source and commercial software. Some of the key applications include CFD (primarily in-house), weather and climate (MOM, WRF), chemistry, material sciences and molecular modelling.

C-MMACS will be looking very keenly at the upcoming accelerator technologies in order to ensure that the future large scale high performance computing is realized with as low a power infrastructure as possible but yet with minimal developmental effort from the users to extract maximum performance. Efforts are already on in this direction.

GPU Computing with Fornax at the Pawsey Centre

Christopher HARRIS
International Centre for Radio Astronomy/UWA, AUSTRALIA

The Pawsey Centre is a HPC facility run by iVEC in Perth, Western Australia. This presentation will provide an introduction to the Pawsey Centre, including details of its two current systems, Epic and the GPU-accelerated Fornax supercomputer. Subsequently, it will describe some of the projects that are utilising this resource. This includes several radio astronomy GPU projects that the presenter has been involved with.

Keynote Lecture

HPC and its Industrial Applications in Japan --- from K Computer to Exaflops

Yoshio OYANAGI
Kobe University, JAPAN

The development of HPC and computational sciences in Japan is compared with that in the U.S. When we youngsters started computational sciences, i.e. scientific research using large scale computation in the 1970's, senior professors were skeptic about it. In the 1980's, however, Japanese vendors started to produce high-quality vector computers and Japanese government deployed them at university and laboratory computer centers. There was a boom of computational sciences. Some industries also equipped with those machines for research and development. They were so user friendly that few users dared to harness parallel computers.

The success of vector computers in Japan caused on the other hand the delay of parallel computer development. In the U.S. a number of venture companies started to build massively parallel computers in the 1980's and users welcomed them. On the contrary there were no Japanese commercial parallel products in the 1980's although parallel research was active in the Japanese academia.

In the late 1990's, Japan started to utilize parallel supercomputers, about 10 years behind the U.S. It should be noted that parallel computers in Japan were initiated by users, not by manufacturers. The K computer was developed by Fujitsu together with computational scientists. We are very eager to deploy supercomputers and computational sciences in industries, e.g. for drug design, new materials and mechanical design.

Japan is now considering the possibility of exa-scale machine(s) in 2018-20. The basic principle of the design is "science driven," i.e. the architecture and system software should be designed from the viewpoint of scientific applications. Japanese government is to fund a feasibility study in 2012-13 fy.

Keynote Lecture

Algorithmic and Software Challenges when Moving Towards Exascale

Jack DONGARRA
Innovative Computing Laboratory, EECS Department, University of Tennessee, Knoxville (UTK),
USA

In this talk we examine how high performance computing has changed over the last 10-year and look toward the future in terms of trends. These changes have had and will continue to have a major impact on our software. Some of the software and algorithm challenges have already been encountered, such as management of communication and memory hierarchies through a combination of compile--time and run--time techniques, but the increased scale of computation, depth of memory hierarchies, range of latencies, and increased run--time environment variability will make these problems much harder.

We will look at five areas of research that will have an importance impact in the development of software and algorithms.

We will focus on following themes:

- Redesign of software to fit multicore and hybrid architectures
- Automatically tuned application software
- Exploiting mixed precision for performance
- The importance of fault tolerance
- Communication avoiding algorithms

Accelerator Session

Intel(r) Many Integrated Core (MIC) Architecture for HPC

David SCOTT
Intel, USA

Intel® Many Integrated Core™ Architecture

Intel has a long history of developing and then integrating co-processors into general purpose processors. Math co-processors and vector units all started as separate off package devices that still used a common programming model. The new Intel high performance product line is based on Intel® MIC architecture targets HPC segments such as oil exploration, scientific research, financial analyses, and climate simulation, among many others. It's codenamed Knights Corner, and Intel is building it on 22-nanometer manufacturing process using transistor structures as small as 22 billionths of a meter. It will scale to more than 50 Intel processing cores on a single chip.

Maintaining productivity is the biggest hurdle when going down a path using co-processor or special purpose devices, like GPGPU's that tie developer efforts to proprietary or unsupported languages for software development. Intel® MIC products give developers a key advantage: They run standard, existing programming tools and methods.

Intel® MIC architecture combines many Intel® CPU cores onto a single chip. Developers can program these cores using standard C, C++, and FORTRAN source code. The same parallel program source code written for Intel® MIC products can be compiled and run on a standard Intel® Xeon processor. Familiar programming models remove developer-training barriers, allowing the developer to focus on the problems rather than software engineering. Because Intel processors are used in over 80% of the world's supercomputers, programmers can continue to work in familiar territory when creating software for the MIC architecture that uses the same tools, compilers, and libraries as the Intel® Xeon processors.

Application Development on GPGPUs: Challenges and Solutions

Anutosh MOITRA
Tata/CRL, INDIA

There are a significant number of systems in the Top500 that use GPGPUs, many of which are in Asia. The main problem that we face is the lack of scalable software that can utilize accelerators for problems that require a few hundred TeraFLOPs. It is also instructive to look beyond the Top500 to systems that are 'small' HPC systems -- of the order of a few TeraFLOPs. Once again, the biggest constraint to widespread adoption of these systems is the availability of applications to GPGPUs.

In this talk, I will present the challenges we have faced in implementing GPGPU based solutions from the domains of oil and gas, fluid dynamics, radar image processing and computational finance. I will propose possible approaches to overcoming these challenges in the immediate future, and a possible longer term solution.

Utilising Different Accelerators - A Programmer's Perspective

Jeff ADIE
SGI, USA

In this presentation, the author recounts his experiences in porting a variety of codes to a variety of accelerator types, including FPGA, GPU and, more recently, Intel MIC. The focus of the presentation is on the 'time and effort' required by the developer to effectively utilise the different technologies rather than the absolute performance gains.

MIC and GPU: Application, Porting and Optimization

Qing JI
Chief Scientist of HPC Application, Inspur (Beijing) Electronic Information Industry Co, LTD, CHINA

As a leading Chinese company of HPC, INSPUR contributed to the construction of supercomputing systems including Tianhe1A and Sunway BlueLight MPP, which were ranked as #1 at TOP500 2010.11 and #14 at TOP500 2011.11, respectively. More recently, the TS10K was set up in collaboration with Tsinghua University, which greatly improved the efficiency of Earth System Simulation with the peak performance of 172Teraflops (highest at Chinese academy).

INSPUR are experienced at the porting & optimization of GPU at broad aspects, such as life science, petroleum; and CFD etc. More important, INSPUR-INTEL China Parallel Computing Joint Lab was founded at 2011 for the sake of exploring the system and application innovation research on Exascale computing. One of our first topics is Many Integrated Core (MIC), which has been successfully incorporated in many projects: PSTM(petroleum), BSDE(finance), GRAPES(weather) and ATOM(Life). The project of ATOM was selected as one of top five showcases of MIC at SC11 for INTEL exhibition.

In this presentation, a first-hand application case will be shared in order to exhibit the differences of composition, application, porting, optimization and productivity between MIC and GPU.

Keynote Lecture

Accelerating System Software for Extreme Scale Computing

Thomas STERLING
Indiana University, USA

Accelerators are becoming pervasive in HPC giving the impression that heterogeneous computing is an emerging capability. Nothing could be further from the truth as heterogeneity has been a

major part of conventional systems for decades. Distinct processors for motherboards, NICs, visualization, and other purposes have been common for most systems. What has changed is that these diverse computing elements are hidden from the programmer and so exhibit the property of homogeneous computing, while the use of GPUs exposes the heterogeneity to the application programmer. But there are other forms of processing that will need to be accelerated if extreme scale computing, including both strong scaled and Exascale computing, will become successful. Over the last two decades, the communicating sequential processes execution model has dominated as reflected by the MPI application-programming interface. But to realize future extreme scale computing an alternative execution model exhibiting a much broader diversity of parallelism forms and dynamic adaptive resource management and task scheduling will become essential. Power, reliability, and performance scale all will demand new system capabilities not currently supported including hardware support in the form of acceleration for new overhead mechanisms. A new and innovative execution model, ParalleX, is being explored to learn what such future accelerator mechanisms should be driven by these needs. Global address space management and translation, active method task instantiation, lightweight powerful synchronization objects, and rapid thread management including context switching are just some of the essential capabilities required to be accelerated for future extreme scale computing systems. This presentation will describe the ParalleX model and discuss the ways in which acceleration of its semantic constructs will dramatically improve scalability and practical operational constraints.

Software Tools Session

ppOpen-HPC: Open Source Infrastructure for Development and Execution of Large-Scale Scientific Applications on Post-Petascale Supercomputers with Automatic Tuning (AT)

Kengo NAKAJIMA
University of Tokyo, JAPAN

We propose an open source infrastructure for development and execution of optimized and reliable simulation codes on post-petascale (pp) parallel computers with heterogeneous computing nodes which consist of multicore CPU's and accelerators., named "ppOpen-HPC". ppOpen-HPC consists of various types of libraries, which covers various types of procedures for scientific computations. Source code developed on a PC with a single processor is linked with these libraries, and generated parallel code is optimized for post-peta-scale system. Capability of automatic tuning is important and critical technology for further development on new architectures and maintenance of the framework.

C-DAC's Efforts : Application Kernels on HPC GPU Cluster

V.C.V. RAO
C-DAC, INDIA

We describe the problem of parallelization of finite difference method (FDM) and finite element method (FEM) computations for certain class of partial differential equations (PDEs) on High Performance Computing (HPC) GPU cluster. For FDM, the structured grids have been employed and optimal data re-arrangement operations are performed in GPU computations. For FEM, unstructured triangular and hexahedral meshes are generated and graph partitioning METIS [14] software is used to generate load-balanced sub-domains. The iterative methods have been used to solve result algebraic matrix system of linear equations. A combination of MPI with CUDA and OpenCL enabled NVIDIA as well as OpenCL based AMD-ATI GPUs of HPC GPU Cluster have been used in our experiments [4,6,7,8]. Our experiments indicate that the MPI-CUDA codes based on

FDM and FEM achieves nearly 6x speed-ups for large mesh sizes in comparison to host-cpu implementation of the same code. The un-optimized OpenCL implementation GPU times have shown marginal improvement in speed-ups whereas counterpart the CUDA codes achieved maximum speedup of 4x to 6x on HPC GPU Cluster. We presented performance analysis for different mesh sizes that prove performance capabilities of performance and scalability of FDM and FEM computations GPU cluster.

Applications Session 3

Challenges and Achievements of GPU-centered HPC using Taiwan's Formosa 4

Matthew SMITH

National Center for High-performance Computing (NCHPC), TAIWAN

Fang-An KUO

NCHC, NARL, TAIWAN

The National Center for High-performance Computing (NCHC) is Taiwan's premier HPC service provider, allowing universities and industrial partners across Taiwan affordable access to modern HPC facilities. Our latest addition is named "Formosa 4" – a system powered by approximately 80 ASUS ESC4000 GPU servers, each with three Tesla GPU computing devices and a single Infiniband 40Gb/s adaptor. The system installation and configuration was completed by our NCHC team in November 2011, and is currently ranked 234 in the Top500 list of supercomputers. The system cost approximately 37 million Taiwan dollars (over 1 million US dollars) and is Taiwan's largest dedicated GPU computation platform.

In addition to being a HPC service provider, the NCHC also serves as a research house, with a competent research team focused on the development of novel algorithms for application to engineering and scientific problems. We will discuss the development and application of several tools for solving hyperbolic systems (such as gas and fluid flows). These solvers have been demonstrated solving unsteady (transient) problems with cell numbers on the order of billions and a reported speedup of several thousand times that compared to the time required using a single Xeon CPU – all using a small fraction of the Formosa 4 cluster. We will present the challenges associated with this solver development, in addition to its application to several industrial problems solved in collaboration with local and international industry. Through efficient algorithm design and programming, we demonstrate that a relatively small GPU cluster can be capable of competing with much larger HPC systems.

Accelerator Session

Accelerating innovation in HPC

Ed TURKEL

HP, USA

As the name implies, high performance computing creates insatiable demands for the performance needed to innovate in science, engineering, analytics and elsewhere. But if HPC were easy, everyone would be doing it. Barriers exist that create challenges to scaling HPC to new levels – now that we've reached petascale performance, the challenge of exascale looms. In this presentation, we'll discuss the performance, efficiency and management challenges we've overcome at petascale, and what's next on the road to exascale.

Software Tools

GPU/CPU collaborative computing technology in seismic data pre-stack migration

Hongwei LIU
CAS/IGG, CHINA

Seismic data pre-stack time migration and depth migration are the most time consuming parts of seismic processing, especially for one-way wave pre-stack depth migration (OWE), and reverse-time migration (RTM). With the continuous deepening of exploration and production, the existing computer resources have been unable to meet the needs. Since 2008, IGGCAS has been dedicated in developing GPU/CPU collaborative computing pre-stack seismic data migration technologies, including asymmetric travel time pre-stack time migration, OWE and RTM. These technologies have been widely used in China in various oil fields and have achieved satisfactory results; this presentation will mainly explain the developing process and applications of these technologies.

Synchronization on GPUs: Performance Curse or Blessing?

Che-Rung LEE
NTHU, TAIWAN

Barrier synchronization, an essential mechanism to ensure the correctness of parallel programming, is regarded as one of the performance threats since a group of processing units need to stop and wait until all in the group reach the same execution point. In this talk, we provide a controversial viewpoint for the synchronization on GPUs: adding barrier synchronizations, even functionally unnecessary, can improve performance on a number of occasions. We first give a simple example code as the empirical evidence, and then propose a memory contention model to explain this phenomenon. Based on the model, we identify a programming pattern that adding artificial barrier synchronizations can improve the performance of programs. Our hypothesis is then verified and supported by the experimental results of synthetic benchmarks and real applications.

Modeling and Optimizing the Performance of Multifrontal Linear System Solver on Hybrid CPU-GPU System

Weichung WANG
Department of Mathematics, National Taiwan University, TAIWAN

Solving a large and sparse symmetric positive definite linear system is at the heart of various scientific and engineering computing. By focusing on the multifrontal method, we investigate how a GPU (NVIDIA C2070) can be used to accelerate the computations. We first propose simple yet effective computation and communication models on a hybrid CPU-GPU system. The models lead to several CPU/GPU workload distribution schemes with the aim to achieve the shortest elapsed runtime. Analytical and numerical results are presented to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed algorithms and implementations.

An Insightful and Quantitative Performance Optimization Chain for GPUs

Yunquan ZHANG
Institute of Software (IoS), CAS, CHINA

It is challenging to optimize GPU kernels because this progress requires deep technical knowledge of the underlying hardware. Modern GPU architectures are becoming more and more diversified,

which further exacerbates the already difficult problem of performance optimization. This paper presents an insightful and quantitative performance optimization chain for GPUs. The goal is to help non-expert programmers with limited knowledge of GPU architectures implement high performance GPU kernels directly. We achieve it by providing performance information to identify GPU program performance bottlenecks and decide which optimization methods should be adopted, so as to facilitate the best match between algorithm features and underlying hardware characteristics. To demonstrate the usage of optimization chain, we optimize three representative GPU kernels with different compute intensity: Matrix Transpose, Laplace Transform and Integral on both NVIDIA and AMD GPUs. Experimental results demonstrate that under the guidance of our optimization chain, performance of those kernels achieves 7.8~42.4 times speedup compared to their naïve implementations on both NVIDIA and AMD GPU platforms.

Implementation of Green computing in IBM HPC software stack on Accelerator based super computer

Nagarajan KATHIRESAN
IBM, INDIA

Today's energy—and climate—related issues are at the top of our strategic agenda. IBM solutions can help customers reduce costs and systemically minimize energy, water, carbon emissions and waste. IBM is helping customers to become more energy efficient, implement new ways to source, manufacture and distribute goods and services in a more sustainable manner, enable safe and renewable sources of energy and manage resources at a macro level, transforming entire industries. IBM takes a holistic approach to our planet's challenges that combines our innovative technology, deep business insight, and industry expertise. Together, we can enhance the sustainability of business-and our planet.

PARRAY: The Array-Based GPU Programming Technology

Yifeng CHEN
School of Electronic Engineering and Computer Science, Peking University, CHINA

This talk introduces a programming interface called PARRAY (or Parallelizing ARRAYS that supports system-level succinct programming for heterogeneous parallel systems like GPU clusters. The current practice of software development requires combining several low-level libraries like Pthread, OpenMP, CUDA and MPI. Achieving productivity and portability is hard with different numbers and models of GPUs. PARRAY extends mainstream C programming with novel array types of the following features: 1) the dimensions of an array type are nested in a tree structure, conceptually reflecting the memory hierarchy; 2) the definition of an array type may contain references to other array types, allowing sophisticated array types to be created for parallelization; 3) threads also form arrays that allow programming in a Single-Program-Multiple-Codeblock (SPMC) style to unify various sophisticated communication patterns. This leads to shorter, more portable and maintainable parallel codes, while the programmer still has control over performance-related features necessary for deep manual optimization. Although the source-to-source code generator only faithfully generates low-level library calls according to the type information, higher-level programming and automatic performance optimization are still possible through building libraries of sub-programs on top of PARRAY. The case study on cluster FFT illustrates a simple 30-line code that 2x-outperforms Intel Cluster MKL on the Tianhe-1A system with 7168 Fermi GPUs and 14336 CPUs.

SnuCL and an MPI+OpenCL Implementation of HPL on Heterogeneous CPU/GPU

Clusters

Jaejin LEE

School of Computer Science and Engineering, Center for Manycore Programming, Seoul National University (SNU), KOREA

SnuCL is an OpenCL framework and freely available, open-source software developed by the Center for Manycore Programming at Seoul National University. SnuCL provides an illusion of a single heterogeneous system (i.e., a single OS instance) for the programmer. A GPU or a set of CPU cores becomes an OpenCL compute device. SnuCL allows the application to utilize compute devices in a remote compute node as if they were in the host node. With SnuCL, OpenCL applications written for a single OS instance and multiple OpenCL compute devices can run on a heterogeneous cluster without any modification. SnuCore is a sixteen-node heterogeneous CPU/GPU cluster that has been built to evaluate software techniques developed in the center. Each node consists of two 12-core CPUs and six GPUs. After porting HPL to SnuCore using MPI+OpenCL and optimizing it with our techniques for multiple GPUs, we have achieved 991 GFLOPS of double-precision performance per node (total 15.9 TFLOPS) and 871 MFLOPS/Watt on SnuCore. Previous LINPACK implementations are focused on an efficient implementation of large-sized matrix operations for accelerators. We argue that this assumption does not hold anymore when each node contains more than two GPUs, and optimizations aimed at reducing the overhead of CPUs are necessary to fully utilize those multiple GPUs. We are planning to incorporate these techniques to the SnuCL framework.

Keynote Lecture

On the road to Exascale: Lessons from Contemporary Scalable GPU Systems

Jeffrey VETTER

Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), USA

Reports from various organizations have identified multiple challenges on the road to Exascale computing. These challenges include the unrelenting issues of performance, scalability, and productivity in the face of ever-increasing complexity; they also include the relatively new priorities of energy-efficiency and resiliency. Not coincidentally, recently announced HPC architectures, such as RoadRunner, Tianhe-1A, Tsubame, Titan, Dash, and Sequoia, illustrate that emerging technologies, such as graphics processors, system-on-a-chip designs, and non-volatile memory can provide innovative solutions to address some of these challenges.

Our early experiences on these systems have demonstrated performance and power benefits; however, we have also experienced major challenges in productivity, portability, and performance stability. Our NSF Keeneland project has deployed a GPU-based system for the NSF user community, and we find that these issues, taken together, are impeding the adoption of these innovative architectures by the broader scientific community. In this talk, I will discuss recent research advances aimed at lowering these productivity barriers for existing systems, and summarize how these lessons can influence future Exascale architectures.

Posters Abstracts

Summed-Area Table Algorithm Optimization Based on the OpenCL

Shengen YAN

Graduate University of Chinese Academy of Sciences , CHINA

Summed-Area table algorithm is also known as image integral algorithm. It is often used for quickly and efficiently generating the sum of values in a rectangular subset of a grid. Our work is based on the OpenCL framework. We have studied various kinds of optimization methods mainly on AMD GPUs. In this paper, we first implemented an efficient prefix sum algorithm. Then we described how to use vectors in detail. We also adopted many other skills. For instance, a workgroup calculates the entire column by using a loop and each workgroup calculates multi-columns. The results show that the optimized algorithm got a good performance on both NVIDIA platform and AMD platform. On the NVIDIA Tesla C2050 GPU, we got a 33% performance boost compared to CUDA NPP. On the AMD HD 5850 platform, the average performance has reached 4.21 times compared to the appropriate CPU version function in OpenCV 2.3.

Hybrid LU Factorization on Multi-GPU Multi-core Heterogeneous Platforms

Yulu Jia

University of Tennessee, USA

LU factorization is an important step in solving systems of linear equations. It's the most computational intensive step compared to the subsequent backward substitution. Hence, to solve systems of linear equations fast requires performing LU factorization fast. Accelerator based approach for linear algebra has regained attention after a dormant period. GPUs are the most important and widely used accelerators nowadays. They are extremely fast for math operations on large data sets which feature high data parallelism. In this work we designed and implemented a hybrid LU factorization on multi-core and multi-GPU heterogeneous platforms. Our algorithm utilizes all the available CPU cores and GPUs. A small number of CPUs are dedicated to factorize the panel, while the rest of the CPU cores and the GPUs are used to update the trailing submatrix. Both dynamic scheduling and static scheduling are used in our algorithm. We carried out experiments on a system with 48 AMD CPUs and 4 Fermi GPUs. We obtained a performance of 1134Gflop/s, which is the best result ever achieved on a shared memory system to our knowledge.

A Highly Scalable Algorithm for N-body Simulation

Daniel Kogler

Indiana University, USA

At present, most algorithms developed for simulating the N-Body problem, and virtually all algorithms used in practice, place an inherent limit on the amount of exploitable parallelism in the form of a global time-step barrier. As a result of this global barrier between each time-step in the simulation, many clock cycles are wasted as processors which have finished computations for that time-step are idle while waiting for other processors to complete their computations. We are exploring methods which could be used to remove this global time-step barrier by making use of the ParalleX model of computation, and in doing so producing a more scalable algorithm capable out-performing current algorithms on large simulations when scaled up to very large computing systems. At present, we have identified three possible techniques for avoiding this global barrier. The techniques in consideration include projection of bodies into future time-steps, space-time clustering of bodies as opposed to special clustering of bodies, and approximating the global-time

solution to the problem. Each of these techniques comes with tradeoffs between simulation accuracy, exploitable parallelism, and introduced overhead. And we are in the process of determining which of these techniques or combinations thereof holds the greatest potential for improved performance.

Parallelizing Molecular Dynamics Solutions For High Performance

Shrinidhi Hudli, Shrihari Hudli, Raghu Hudli, Yashonath Subramanian and T.S. Mohan
M.S. Ramaiah Institute of Technology, ObjectOrb Technologies, Indian Institute of Science and Infosys, Bangalore, INDIA

Molecular Simulation (MD) programs have very long running times. They involve solving Lagrangian equations of motion of a system of N particles. MD simulation involves computing electromagnetic forces between particles whose computational complexity is $O(n^2)$. Using some techniques to speed up and parallelizing computations, we not only reduced the complexity of $O(n)$, but also reduced the constant to achieve an overall speed up of 200X for large problem sizes on NVIDIA Tesla GPGPU. Our algorithm exploits data parallelism in the MD problem and makes efficient allocation of threads dynamically based on the problem size to achieve high speed up.

Automated Mapping Streaming Applications to GPUs

Huynh Phung Huynh, Rick Siow Mong Goh
A*STAR IHPC, SINGAPORE

Andrei Hagiescu
Altera, SINGAPORE

Weng Fai Wong
NUS, SINGAPORE

In this poster, we describe our automated compilation flow that maps most stream processing applications onto a single GPU or Multi-GPU systems. The challenges of mapping streaming applications to GPUs are: (1) How to utilize GPU memory hierarchy efficiently? (2) How to minimize communication overhead intra/inter GPUs. (3) How to generate GPU code automatically for streaming application that takes into account GPU architecture-specific parameters. Tackling those challenges, we made the following key contributions : (1) A novel memory access scheme that uses a mix of compute and memory access threads to maximize the effectiveness of the GPU memory hierarchy. This scheme results in high performance and throughputs for the streaming applications mapped to GPUs. (2) A scalable framework that maps efficiently most streaming applications to CPU + Multi-GPU systems. (3) Automated GPU code generator from StreamIt (an open source streaming programming language from MIT) code. The generated GPU code can be tailored efficiently to different GPU architectures.

A SnuCL Implementation of the LINPACK Benchmark on Clusters with Multi-GPU Nodes

Gangwon Jo, Jeongho Nah, Jungwon Kim, Jun Lee, and Jaejin Lee
Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul 151-744, KOREA

Site Visit Briefs

Genome Institute of Singapore

The Genome Institute of Singapore (GIS) is the national flagship program for the genomic sciences in Singapore. The core values of GIS are scientific integration, medical focus and internationalization.

A*STAR is the parent funding body for the GIS and has a long term commitment to create a world-class infrastructure.

In October 2003, the new research building, the Genome - a 7,200 sq. meter advanced facility, was inaugurated. Set in the Biopolis - a 180 hectare biomedical city within the Buona Vista Science Hub, the Genome is adjacent to other biomedical institutes such as Singapore's Institute of Molecular Biology and Cell Biology, the Bioinformatics Institute, the Institute of Biomedical Engineering, the Biotechnology Institute, the Biomedical Research Council, regional and multinational industrial R&D organizations. The Biopolis provides an excellent environment conducive to the exchange of knowledge and collegial interactions. It was planned as a complete community that supports living, working, learning and playing: combining state-of-art research infrastructure with entertainment and educational facilities.

Bioinformatics Institute

The Bioinformatics Institute (BII) was set up by A*STAR in July 2001; it was re-launched with a strong scientific program in the autumn months of 2007. Located in the Biopolis, BII is conceived as the computational biology research and postgraduate training institute as well as a national resource centre in bioinformatics within the Biomedical Research Council (BMRC) of A*STAR.

The BII focuses on theoretical approaches aimed at understanding biomolecular mechanisms that underlie biological phenomena, the development of computational methods to support this discovery process, and experimental verification of predicted molecular and cellular functions of genes and proteins with biochemical methods.

Together with the BMRC, A*STAR research institutes and multinational R&D organizations in the Biopolis, the BII is situated in a conducive environment for exchange of scientific knowledge and friendly interaction that will prompt greater collaborations, and position the Biopolis as a notable biomedical R&D hub in Asia and in the world.

Institute of High Performance Computing

At Institute of High Performance Computing (IHPC), a common vision is shared in establishing the Institute as the computing powerhouse for Singapore and the region. Through IHPC's unique scientific capabilities and world-leading R&D efforts, we capitalize on the power of computational science to solve major scientific, engineering and industrial problems.

Our activities are spread over a wide range of topics such as:

- solid mechanics,
- fluid dynamics,
- coupled solid/fluid mechanics,
- materials science/condensed matter physics,
- chemistry,
- electromagnetics,
- photonics and plasmonics,
- solid-state electronics,
- biophysics, and
- cognitive science.

Each area is helmed by an accomplished senior scientist/engineer, and they are complemented by

researchers advancing the field of high performance computing itself — through the development of advanced HPC software and computer architectures, adaptive and collaborative computing, computational geometry, modeling and visualization, and data-analytics.

IHPC strive to push the frontiers of scientific inquiry through our expertise in high performance computing, and we welcome strategic partnerships that would build new capabilities and enhance existing strengths.

Through the development of long-term ties with industry partners, including multinational companies and local SMEs, to ensure that our R&D activities stay focused and relevant to real-world needs, we are focused on solving real-world problems for better value-add to Singapore and society at large.

Institute for Infocomm Research

The Institute for Infocomm Research (I²R pronounced as i-squared-r) is a member of the Agency for Science, Technology and Research (A*STAR) family. Established in 2002, I²R's mission is to be the globally preferred source of innovations in 'Interactive Secured Information, Content and Services Anytime Anywhere' through research by passionate people dedicated to Singapore's economic success. I²R performs R&D in information, communications and media (ICM) technologies to develop holistic solutions across the ICM value chain. Our research capabilities are in information technology, wireless and optical communication networks, interactive and digital media, signal processing and computing. We seek to be the infocomm and media value creator that keeps Singapore ahead.

Institute of Materials Research and Engineering

The Institute of Materials Research and Engineering (IMRE) is a research institute of the Science and Engineering Research Council (SERC) under A*STAR. The Institute has capabilities in materials analysis & characterisation, design & growth, patterning & fabrication, and synthesis & integration. We house a range of state-of-the-art equipment for materials research including development, processing and characterisation. IMRE conducts a wide range of research, which includes novel materials for organic solar cells, photovoltaics, printed electronics, catalysis, biomimetics, microfluidics, quantum dots, heterostructures, sustainable materials, atom technology, etc. We collaborate actively with other research institutes, universities, public bodies, and a wide spectrum of industrial companies, both globally and locally.

National University Singapore, High Performance Computing Centre

In a research environment, HPC is the use of hardware, software, tools and programming techniques to accelerate research computation, which in turn will enable the execution of large cutting-edge research simulation that accelerates new discoveries. At the National University of Singapore, a combination of centralized and distributed approaches has been adopted in the provisioning and support of HPC for research computation. In this hybrid environment, some departments and research groups are providing local resources to support their users, whereas the HPC team at the NUS Computer Centre is focusing on providing central HPC resources and services to support all staff and student researchers across campus.

Central HPC support at NUS Computer Centre began in 1989 when a shared vector supercomputer was made available to the NUS research community. Since then, a variety of HPC systems and technologies had been introduced to meet wide range of research computing requirements, which include cc-NUMA multi-processor system, Linux and Windows based cluster parallel computing system, remote visualization system, parallel file system, Grid computing resources, and more recently the GPU system and the HPC private cloud technology.

**Nanyang Technological University,
School of Physical and Mathematical Sciences
&
High Performance Computing Center**

The High Performance Computing Centre (HPCC) in NTU provides computational resources to the entire research community in the University and manages one of ASEAN's greenest supercomputing cluster with a PUE 1.4 in a tropical and humid climate. The facility has a floor space of 123m² cluster and houses more than 300 IBM System x iDataplex compute servers with more than 2500 Intel® Xeon® processor 5500-series processors and has a measured computing power (Rmax) of over 29 teraflops (trillion mathematical calculations per second).

About A*CRC

A*STAR Computational Resource Centre provides high performance computational (HPC) resources to the entire A*STAR research community. Currently A*CRC supports HPC needs of over seven hundred strong user community and manages several high-end computers. It is also responsible for very rapidly growing data storage resources.

A*CRC operates two data centers located at the Fusionopolis and Biopolis, both ultra modern facilities located close to each other in the One-North –the new science and technology hub area in the west of downtown Singapore.

A*CRC is divided into five functional areas: i) Computational Systems, ii) Storage, iii) Networking, iv) Operations, and v) HPC Software. An integral part of A*CRC activities is HPC users' support. A*CRC also plans the future high-end hardware requirements of A*STAR and is responsible for tender and procurement processes.

About ATIP

The Asian Technology Information Program (ATIP) provides customized and standard products and services focusing on Asian technology trends, research, policy, and market strategies. Our customers are government, industry, and non-profit organizations worldwide. We utilize our on-the-ground experts to get only the most up-to-date and accurate information.

ATIP produces at least 50 publications annually. Each ATIP Report (averaging about 15 pages) is written by an expert technology analyst on a specific topic or event, and includes significant analysis and comparative assessment. Publications span a very broad range of both technology topics and geographic coverage. A preview of current publications are available on the ATIP website.

Acknowledgement

The organising committee wishes to express its sincere appreciation to:

Our Guest of Honour, Dr. Raj THAMPURAN
Executive Director, SERC, A*STAR

All speakers and participants

All Sponsors

All staff who made this conference possible.

ERRATA:

Infrastructure Session (11:45 - 12:00 Monday 7th May 2012)
Discovery Theatre

Stuck with I/O

Alf Wachsman
Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology (OIST), JAPAN

The Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology is a brand new graduate university on Okinawa, Japan. Japan's first international university, OIST does research in life sciences and physics. Many computing applications at OIST, like gene sequencing, are very data intense and this data needs to be accessible from many different platforms (Windows PCs, HPC cluster, Mac OS). I will present OIST's existing data infrastructure and show new performance results for various file system options on this and newer hardware. I/O capabilities will become increasingly crucial as new generation of high-performance CPUs and GPUs become available.

11:25	Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO), INDIA	<i>CFD Code on GPUs for Aerospace Applications</i>	Tohoku U, JAPAN	<i>Platforms</i>
11:25 - 11:45	Mahendra K. VERMA Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur (IITK), INDIA	<i>Object-oriented Pseudo-spectral Code TARANG for Turbulence Simulation</i>	William LU Platform, USA	<i>Accelerating your HPC Environment</i>
11:45 - 12:00	P.B. Sunil KUMAR IIT Madras, INDIA	<i>Thermostat for Colloidal Dynamics Simulations: Some Challenges</i>	Alf Wachsman Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology (OIST) JAPAN	<i>Stuck with I/O</i>
12:00 - 12:15	Q & A Session			
12:15 - 13:00	Lunch - Food Court at Matrix Building, Biopolis			
Location	Exploration Theatre			
13:00 - 13:40	Keynote 2 Taisake BOKU University of Tsukuba, JAPAN	<i>HA-PACS Project: Challenge for Next Step of Accelerated Computing</i>		
Location	Exploration Theatre		Discovery Theatre	
	Chair: TBA Applications 2A: Molecular Dynamics		Chair: Tin Wee TAN Applications 2B: Genomics, etc.	
13:40 - 14:00	Long Wang Computer Network and Information Center, CAS, CHINA	<i>SC_PEtot: A Plane Wave Pseudopotential Density Functional Theory Code on GPU Clusters</i>	Bingqiang WANG BGI, CHINA	<i>Accelerate High Throughput Analysis for Genome Sequencing with GPU</i>
14:00 - 14:20	Chun HUANG School of Computer, National University of	<i>Accelerating Molecular Dynamics on Heterogeneous Petascale Supercomputer</i>	Victor A KOSTYUCHENKO Duke-NUS Singapore,	<i>CUDA Technology Applications in Studies of Disease-causing Viruses</i>

	Defense Technology (NUDT), CHINA		SINGAPORE	
14:20 - 14:40	Rio YOKOTA King Abdullah University of S&T, SAUDI ARABIA	<i>Scaling Fast Multipole Methods up to 4000 GPUs</i>	Hongsuk YI KISTI Supercomputing Center, KOREA	<i>Hardware Accelerators in Scientific Applications: A Monte Carlo Case Study</i>
14:40 - 14:50	Q & A Session			
14:50 - 15:05	Coffee/Tea Break			
Location	Exploration Theatre			
15:05 - 15:40	Keynote 3 Nadia THALMANN Nanyang Technological University, SINGAPORE	<i>Virtual Try On: An Application That Needs GPU Acceleration</i>		
	Chair: TBA Graphics, Visualisation, Imaging		Chair: Jeffrey VETTER Infrastructure & Activities	
15:40 - 16:10	Wojtek GOSCINSKI Monash University, AUSTRALIA	<i>The Multi-Modal Australian ScienceS Imaging and Visualisation Environment (MASSIVE)</i>	R.P. THANGAVELU CMMACS, INDIA	<i>CSIR Initiatives in Petascale Computing</i>
16:10 - 16:40	Guangming TAN Institute of Computing Technology (ICT), CAS, CHINA	<i>Single-particle 3D Reconstruction on Specialized Stream Architecture and Comparison with GPGPUs</i>	Christopher HARRIS International Centre for Radio Astronomy/UWA, AUSTRALIA	<i>GPU Computing with Fornax at the Pawsey Centre</i>
16:40 - 16:50	Q & A Session			
Location	Exploration Theatre			
16:50 - 17:30	Keynote 4 Yoshio OYANAGI, Kobe U, JAPAN	<i>HPC and its Industrial Applications in Japan --- from K Computer to Exaflops</i>		
18:00 - 20:00	Dinner at Yunnan Garden Restaurant, Nanyang Technological University Alumni Club			
8 May 2012				
Location	Exploration Theatre			

Time	Speaker	Title		
08:30 - 09:10	Keynote 5 Jack DONGARRA Innovative Computing Laboratory, EECS Department, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, USA	<i>Algorithmic and Software Challenges when Moving Towards Exascale</i>		
09:10 - 09:40	David SCOTT, Intel, USA	<i>Intel(r) Many Integrated Core (MIC) Architecture for HPC</i>		
09:40 - 10:00	Anutosh MOITRA, Tata/CRL, INDIA	<i>Application Development on GPGPUs: Challenges and Solutions</i>		
10:00 - 10:15	Jeff ADIE, SGI, USA	<i>Utilising Different Accelerators - A Programmer's Perspective</i>		
10:15 - 10:35	Qing JI Chief Scientist of HPC Application, Inspur (Beijing) Electronic Information Industry Co, LTD, CHINA	<i>MIC and GPU: Application, Porting and Optimization</i>		
10:35 - 10:45	Q & A Session			
10:45 - 11:00	Coffee/Tea Break			
11:00 - 11:40	Keynote 6 Thomas STERLING Indiana University, USA	<i>Accelerating System Software for Extreme Scale Computing</i>		
Location	Exploration Theatre		Discovery Theatre	
	Chair: Michael LEVINE Software Tools		Chair: Wei GE Applications 3	
11:40 - 12:10	Kengo NAKAJIMA University of Tokyo, JAPAN	<i>ppOpen-HPC: Open Source Infrastructure for Development and Execution of Large-Scale Scientific Applications on Post-Petascale Supercomputers with Automatic Tuning</i>	Matthew SMITH National Center for High-performance Computing (NCHPC), TAIWAN	<i>Challenges and Achievements of GPU- centered HPC using Taiwan's Formosa 4</i>
12:10 - 12:30	V.C.V. RAO C-DAC, INDIA	<i>C-DAC's Efforts : Application Kernels on HPC GPU Cluster</i>	Fang-An KUO NCHC,NARL,TAIWAN	<i>Presenting w/ Matthew Smith</i>
12:30 - 12:40	Q & A Session			
12:40 - 13:15	Lunch - Food Court at Matrix Building, Biopolis			

Location	Exploration Theatre			
13:45 - 14:20	Ed TURKEL, HP, USA	<i>Accelerating Innovation in HPC</i>		
Location	Exploration Theatre		Discovery Theatre	
	Chair: Satoshi MATSUOKA Software Tools		Chair: Jack DONGARRA Software Tools	
14:20 - 14:40	Hongwei LIU CAS/IGG, CHINA	<i>GPU/CPU Collaborative Computing Technology in Seismic Data Pre-stack Migration</i>	Weichung WANG Department of Mathematics, National Taiwan University, TAIWAN	<i>Modeling and Optimizing the Performance of Multifrontal Linear System Solver on Hybrid CPU-GPU System</i>
14:40 - 15:00	Che-Rung LEE NTHU, TAIWAN	<i>Synchronization on GPUs: Performance Curse or Blessing?</i>	Yunquan ZHANG Institute of Software (IoS), CAS, CHINA	<i>An Insightful and Quantitative Performance Optimization Chain for GPUs</i>
15:00 - 15:10	Q & A Session			
15:10 - 15:25	Coffee/Tea Break			
Location	Exploration Theatre			
15:25 - 16:00	Nagarajan KATHIRESAN IBM, INDIA	<i>Implementation of Green Computing in IBM HPC Software Stack on Accelerator based Super Computer</i>		
	Chair: Thomas STERLING Software Tools			
16:00 - 16:20	Yifeng CHEN School of Electronic Engineering and Computer Science, Peking University, CHINA	<i>PARRAY: The Array-Based GPU Programming Technology</i>		
16:20 - 16:40	Jaejin LEE School of Computer Science and Engineering, Center for Manycore Programming, Seoul National University (SNU), KOREA	<i>SnuCL and an MPI+OpenCL Implementation of HPL on Heterogeneous CPU/GPU Clusters</i>		
16:40 - 16:50	Q & A Session			
16:50 - 17:30	Keynote 7	<i>On the Road to Exascale: Lessons from Contemporary Scalable GPU Systems</i>		

	Jeffrey VETTER Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), USA	
17:30 - 18:00		Panel
18:00 - 18:10	Final Remarks	

Tutorial Timetable

Time	Tutorial	Location
9 May 2012		
08:30 – 12:30	Basic nVidia Cuda training	Exploration Theatrette
08:30 – 12:30	Intel MIC Workshop	Discovery Theatrette
14:00 – 16:00	CAPS Enterprise Workshop	Exploration Theatrette
10 May 2012		
08:30 – 12:30	Advanced nVidia Cuda training	Exploration Theatrette